

Subprime Impact Crisis. Libraries, politics and digital sovereignty¹

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Summary

At almost all stages of the research cycle, there is an increasing dependence on a small number of commercial providers, with these providers sometimes directly limiting what research can achieve in terms of work opportunities and questions. Politics, funding bodies and governance are responding to this by attempting to strengthen digital sovereignty. In terms of specific measures, they are meeting with concepts of open science that also seek to combine scientific and societal relevance while safeguarding scientific autonomy and freedom of choice. A central point is a change in reputation structures, which has a direct impact on infrastructural requirements such as the bloated and misguided publication system. Strengthening the digital sovereignty of scientific infrastructures also makes it possible to improve the social obligation of science and thus to push back the influence of the »merchants of doubt« and the science scepticism they promote. This also requires corresponding efforts on the part of libraries.

Keywords

Information infrastructures; surveillance publishing; merchants of doubt; digital sovereignty; scientific governance; open science

The bubble

In the prologue to his book »Subprime Attention Crisis«, Tim Hwang describes a visit to the heart of the internet's money machine - the *Programmatic I/O* trade fair, which brings together the digital advertising industry to exchange ideas in the data-driven marketing ecosystem. Sessions on „best practices for advanced TV measurement“ and „the future of video ad serving“ passed him by, while his congress bag was filled with brochures on „data monetisation with bulletproof tech“ and „ideation, production and approvals of your branded content ... streamlined with unprecedented efficiency.“²

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² Hwang (2020) 3.

Hwang was all the more surprised by one of the opening presentations by Nico Neumann, who, unlike the other congress participants, had nothing to sell, but instead presented his research findings as an Assistant Professor at the Centre for Business Analytics at Melbourne Business School. For Hwang, they were quite something: Neumann was able to show that the data basis for online ad targeting (i.e. what follows us everywhere as tracking) is often flawed, that targeted advertising does not work at all, is also considerably more expensive than traditional approaches, and that the increasingly popular AI and machine learning approaches are misleading - under laboratory conditions, an exemplary relationship between advertising and sales is reversed into the negative, while the statistical models commonly used in the industry suggest a high positive correlation. So why are these technologies so popular? Because, as marketing technologies themselves, they have such great marketing potential that many cannot resist the glamour of an impressively designed dashboard.

„Nico is being very friendly and polite about all this as he goes on. But the core of his talk remains: the data used in targeting ads are garbage. The algorithms being used to deliver advertising are garbage. Nico concludes that old-school mass marketing, without targeting and audience data, will create better ROIs in many situations.‘ The whole edifice of online advertising is, in short, bunk.“³

Hwang describes how Neumann asked for feedback at the end of his presentation. In a hall with hundreds of visitors, not a hand was raised, Neumann was escorted from the podium and the congress continued with the programme. Hwang was left puzzled: how could it be that such important problems were being stubbornly ignored? Was it a lack of understanding or a deeper design flaw in this industry? What would be the consequences for the Internet and the web economy as a whole, which are so dependent on functioning advertising markets? Hwang set out to find out, and what he presents in his book is „less a picture of modern, data-driven wizards of consumer persuasion, and more a murky story of perverse incentives, outright fraud, and a web economy on the brink.“⁴

The title »Subprime Attention Crisis« already describes Hwang’s central argument: that the current structure of the commoditisation of our attention threatens to become a revenant of the subprime mortgage financial crisis of 2007. The market for digital advertising is growing at an explosive rate: Hwang estimates a volume of \$273.3 billion for 2018 and \$427.3 billion for 2022. This trend continues unabated: the Statista portal expects digital advertising expenditure to reach 676.8 billion euros in 2024 and projects a figure of 885.1 billion euros for 2028.⁵ It seems understandable that Hwang sees a threatening bubble looming here.

³ Hwang (2020) 6.

⁴ Hwang (2020) 7.

⁵ See Statista (2023).

For Hwang, the real threat lies in the fact that complete opacity is once again opening up in a huge market. Just as in the run-up to the global financial crisis, a significant proportion of players in derivatives trading no longer understood the individual products until they turned out to be »weapons of math destruction«⁶, the digital attention economy is currently flooding the market with more and more subprime assets in the same way as reflected in Neumann's research findings. Ever larger parts of the market would be completely out of sight and out of reach of buyers, as algorithmic trading, dark pools and new intermediaries smothered all possible critical enquiries under an ever darker blanket of complexity.⁷

This development not only makes the attention economy ripe for a future implosion that could eclipse the dotcom crisis of a quarter of a century ago on an unfathomable scale, but also makes it highly susceptible to criminal exploitation at present. Here, Hwang touches on the analysis of advertising expert Bob Hoffman, who in his book »Adscam« describes complexity as the great friend of fraud. He gleefully presents screenshots of a newsletter from the Association of National Advertisers, which in 2022, in a rare moment of honesty, estimated the scope of advertising fraud at \$80-120 billion annually (i.e. around 20% of global revenue) - only to delete the newsletter the next day. Fraud and manipulation in the digital advertising economy would be the second largest source of criminal income worldwide in 2025 after drug trafficking.⁸

Hoffman's remarks thus also illustrate the limits of Hwang's analogy: although the prehistory of the global financial crisis benefited from political conditions, it was initially essentially an internal market event, and only its virulence had a resounding effect in many areas. The impending subprime attention crisis, on the other hand, is already a vehicle for many things, judging by the examples given by Hoffman: political and geopolitical interests, terrorist financing, military activities, the flourishing security industry, radicalisation, exploitation and genocide - an instrument for all of this is swelling to ever more threatening proportions in the dark opacity and speechlessness of the actors shown by Hwang.

Subprime Impact Crisis

The commoditisation of our attention is overarching: libraries, science policy and scientific governance have also been observing a change in the attention economy in their field for a long time. At the latest since Martina Franzen's study "Breaking News", it has also become clear that this change is having a considerable impact on the forms of science communication.⁹ After a long phase of economic concentration of relevant providers in the science sector, initial studies¹⁰

⁶ See O'Neil (2016).

⁷ See Hwang (2020) 59-74.

⁸ Cf. Hoffman (2022) 45f. and 38.

⁹ Cf. Franzen (2011).

¹⁰ See e.g. Lynch (2017), Hanson (2019), DFG (2021) and Siems (2022).

uncovered data tracking in science, a discussion about the role of data analytics and the use of digital advertising technology in science communication also emerged,¹¹ in which the term *surveillance publishing* became established.¹² Since then, it has become clear that the structures that Hwang shows in their threatening nature are becoming ever more closely intertwined with the former separated ecosystem of science - not least because relevant players are the same on both sides.¹³

The process by which scientific service providers become data traders and potential fairgoers of *Programmatic I/O* can be vividly studied in a white paper from Hum.¹⁴ In the language of programmatic advertising, interested publishers are given guidance on which data to collect themselves, which they can exchange with other publishers or collect reciprocally and also which are worth buying, such as AMA's *Physicians Masterfile* with data from over 1.4 million doctors, medical students and other groups of people in the USA. Audience building, profiling, personalisation and helpful tips on the value of a customer data platform round off the guide. Science, which has laid down clear ideas on correct working practices and ethical behaviour in its rules of good scientific practice, is thus being infiltrated by the practices of an industry that primarily sells an illusion of measurability and claims responsibility in cookie banners and marketing at most,¹⁵ and elegant dashboards are increasingly being added to the long-established key figures and rankings in the everyday life of science (administration). New names and partners are also being introduced, for example when a supplier such as Lehmanns recruits Palantir's Head of Strategy Europe for its training events.¹⁶

The number of subprime assets is also increasing, as the incentive structures of an APC-driven open access transformation are leading to more and more cases in which publishers such as Elsevier and Wiley are pressurising the editors of their journals to generate more article output - and throwing them out the door when they reply that there aren't that many good papers.¹⁷ Meanwhile, Springer is filling up its e-book packages with AI-generated texts and is excited about the possibilities.¹⁸ This enthusiasm is not necessarily shared by the scientists working in the publication infrastructures. They are more concerned that „the colonisation of academia by artificial

¹¹ Cf. Schimank (2023).

¹² Cf. Pooley (2022).

¹³ Cf. Lamdan (2023).

¹⁴ Cf. Hum (n.d.) and the description in Lauer (2022).

¹⁵ For actual practice, see e.g. Adalytics (2024) and Christl and Toner (2024).

¹⁶ See the event website <https://lehmannsbib.de/digitales-anwenderforum-2022-transformation-gestalten-copy/>, accessed on 14/01/2023.

¹⁷ Cf. "The Future of Design Studies Journal", <https://www.designresearchsociety.org/articles/the-future-of-design-studies-journal>, accessed 14 January 2024, and Weinberg (2023).

¹⁸ Cf. e.g. <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-030-16800-1>, <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-030-74713-8> and the press release <https://group.springernature.com/en/group/media/machine-generated-book-with-new-ki-based-book-format/19134730>, accessed on 14 January 2024.

intelligence technologies may erode, deskill and degrade core academic activities, where the role of key actors historically involved in the evaluation of research could become less and less tangible and significant.“ The data-driven exploitation of research and the interactions of academics in publication infrastructures is evidently at the forefront - quality issues are becoming secondary.¹⁹ So what we are looking at here is a *subprime impact crisis* that we cannot say how far it has already progressed because it is also met with a corresponding speechlessness. „So far the publishers' data-hoovering hasn't galvanised scholars to protest“, notes Jeff Pooley with similar irritation to Hwang. He lists many warnings, many analyses of the currently emerging *large language publishing* with a sobering result: „None of this has translated into much, not even awareness among the larger academic public.“²⁰

As in the subprime attention crisis, the speechlessness in the subprime impact crisis is partly due to the opacity of the market in the scientific attention economy. Just as in digital advertising and services, where buyers are deprived of a view of things by an ever more complex layer of intermediaries, which leads to lengthy glossaries in the specialist literature in order to distinguish the DSP (Demand-Side Platform) from the TCF (Transparency & Consent Framework) and the SSP (Supply-Side Platform) and the RTB (Real Time Bidding), there are also an increasing number of intermediaries in the scientific sector that researchers have generally never heard of - unless they attract attention with threats such as the Researchfish service,²¹ , which promptly qualified it for an attractive takeover.²² Instead, the only thing that both researchers and libraries, funders and governance are aware of is the feeling of ever-increasing pressure and the inevitability of giving more and more to this market, while its opacity, like a black hole, causes all the resources that become available to it to disappear and grow ever larger.

The extent of the black hole and its consequences are increasingly being measured. For their study »Papers and patents are becoming less disruptive over time«, Michael Park, Erin Leahey and Russel J. Park analysed a corpus of articles spanning decades, in which a manageable 52,571 published articles were indexed in 1950, compared to 1.1 million in 2010.²³ This overflowing flood of publications would be received or even cited ever more selectively. Researchers would plug their ears, so to speak, and retreat into ever smaller niches that only promise incremental progress, in order to make these too unmanageable with ever more small-scale publications. Even if a replication study has now mitigated the conclusions of less disruptiveness for this period,²⁴ the

¹⁹ See Gendron, Andrew and Cooper 2022.

²⁰ Pooley (2024).

²¹ Cf. Inge (2022).

²² Cf. Magee (2022).

²³ See Park, Leahey and Funk (2023).

²⁴ Cf. Holst et al. (2024).

development shown has by no means stopped: In 2022, the volume of indexed articles had already risen to 2.82 million, meaning it has far more than doubled in little more than a decade, with a corresponding further increase in impact inflation.²⁵ Even though the number of researchers worldwide has increased significantly in recent years, this inflation in the publishing industry ultimately means that publishing is gradually replacing other key research activities: more and more articles have to be generated from less and less lab time, fieldwork and source study in order to keep up with the competition in the »artificial markets«.²⁶

This development cannot be sustainable or even sustained at the current pace without damaging the quality, relevance and stability of science - not to mention the hoped-for disruptive findings. It is therefore certainly not surprising that 71% of postdocs in Germany and still 20% of professors are currently considering leaving the academic system.²⁷ »Leaving academia« is booming with a whole range of information portals, advice literature and coaching offers - the brain drain is obvious and will become even more critical for the state-funded academic sector in the future in view of demographic change. However, it is part of the subprime impact crisis that the destructiveness of the development has so far mainly affected researchers and otherwise remains largely unaddressed, as publishers can expand their production (and other services), libraries fill their virtual magazines, process invoices and describe with metadata, and funding bodies and sponsors receive their metrics. While some benefit, others can continue to wander into the ever deeper and narrower tunnel of their path dependency, while the bubble grows ever larger.

Digital sovereignty

Despite the widespread speechlessness, this development has of course not gone uncriticised: In some respects, perspectives of open science are increasingly meeting with those from politics and governance, who have adopted the concept of digital sovereignty for this purpose. Both groups often have similar things in mind: strategic autonomy, reducing dependencies, developing alternatives, social relevance, safeguarding scientific processes.²⁸ The establishment of the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) in Germany is an example of this: not only does it secure one of the few areas that is at least still largely in the hands of science, but the funding was not awarded according to metrics, but the definition of the procedure includes terms such as »scholarly-led«, »scientific discipline« and »infrastructure-related«.²⁹

²⁵ Cf. Hanson et al. (2023).

²⁶ See Welpé and Brembs (2019).

²⁷ See Fabian, Heger and Fedzin (2024) 5.

²⁸ Cf. e.g. Holzer (2022).

²⁹ See Section 6 of the Bund-Länder-Vereinbarung zu Aufbau und Förderung einer Nationalen Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) of 26 November 2018, BAnz AT 21.12.2018 B10, <https://www.gwk-bonn.de/fileadmin/Redaktion/Dokumente/Papers/NFDI.pdf>, accessed on 14.01.2024.

The perspective of politics and governance is thus clearly characterised by thoughts on safeguards, which has become even more pronounced in recent years: not only the observation that providers have become quasi-regulators in the entire digital science sector, virtually allocating resources and determining their use, but the pandemic and the »Zeitenwende« in particular have created an awareness that societies and the international order have become fragile and that this also has an impact on the role and possibilities of science. The German Council of Science and Humanities's current recommendations on the sovereignty and security of science in the digital space³⁰ pose the question of how security can be organised despite heterogeneity and openness, i.e. the core of the scientific self-image. To this end, the German Council of Science and Humanities believes that the digital empowerment of scientific institutions must be strengthened, i.e. their internal governance and prioritisation, as well as cyber security and cooperation and networking in the development and operation of digital infrastructures and services. This means profile building through the pooling of expertise based on the division of labour and thus the end of local »full-range suppliers«. Procurement and awarding processes are another focal point, as possible changes of provider as well as plurality and openness must be taken into account here. Above all, however, this openness must also be ensured by a sufficient range of publicly funded infrastructures and platforms such as NFDI and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). All of this is not just a temporary endeavour, as shaping the digital space is a permanent task.

The recommendations are densely argued and provide many detailed comments, but overall they take too little account of the incentive structures of the subprime impact crisis, all of which threaten to thwart the important priorities of the German Council of Science and Humanities: if the next paper is the most important thing, researchers will (have to) subordinate everything else to it and use what is easy to use, potent and available in their everyday digital lives - i.e. offers from hyperscalers or specialised data analytics companies. Researchers who use secure, sustainable and sovereign tools, document their software, process their data and make it available for reuse will tend to be pushed out of the system because all of this costs time for publishing and is not rewarded with a scientific reputation. The latter aspect in particular is not pursued further in the recommendations. Data tracking by the major publishers is mentioned, but not the fact that they buy up many applications and companies along the research life cycle and thus extend the constraints of the publication system to electronic lab books, writing tools, research information systems - where data can flow out everywhere and portability and interoperability are not guaranteed.³¹ Such points show that parts of the digital infrastructure, and in particular the libraries,

³⁰ Cf. Wissenschaftsrat (2023).

³¹ See Siems (2023).

are still ultimately underexposed in policy advice and have not been the subject of fundamental analyses and evaluations for a long time.

Dorothea Wagner adopts such a fundamental perspective in her farewell speech as outgoing Chair of the German Council of Science and Humanities.³² In view of the current multiple crises, she believes that the current governance structures of science are exhausted. In her view, the overemphasis on competition, which was also prompted by earlier recommendations from the German Council of Science and Humanities, has led to an increase in performance, but not yet to a contribution to the further development of society that also addresses the need for transformation - because it takes a purely internal perspective: Researchers must be convincing in peer reviewing and thus serve the internal perspective of the discipline. What knowledge is still missing from a societal perspective does not have to play a role here; the common good and transfer have no relevant status in this respect. Digital sovereignty has the same disadvantage, for example in the case of infrastructures that make research possible in the first place and are simply taken for granted. Wagner's position here is one that is also becoming increasingly widespread in science policy, with Baden-Württemberg's Science Minister Olschowski declaring that the time when „science did too little to meet the expectations and needs of society“ is over; the change that needs to take place in society can neither be achieved without the necessary new technologies nor without the equally necessary social innovations. Research funding is now focussed on this, even if it naturally continues to protect fundamental research.³³

In addition to the preference for the internal perspective, Wagner believes that the overemphasis on competition also causes a lack of synthesis of knowledge: competition rewards the new and thus ever deeper disciplinary specialisation, while (overarching) integration and thus the development of knowledge that has already been acquired falls behind. This is what can be seen in the increasing number of publications and this also hinders the use and discussion of scientific findings for society as a whole.

Further points in her argumentation then relate to what is outlined here as the subprime impact crisis, e.g. what she calls the „cynical use of knowledge“: the structure of the attention economy makes it particularly easy for the »merchants of doubt«³⁴ to paralyse science as organised doubt by instrumentalising this very doubt in order to delay necessary regulations for Big Tobacco, the fossil fuel industry, etc., in some cases for decades, with considerable consequences for society. It should be added here that the rise of the »doubt industry« runs parallel to the corresponding rise of publishing companies: it was the rise of Robert Maxwell and his business model of scientific

³² Cf. Wagner (2023).

³³ Cf. Olschowski (2023).

³⁴ See Oreskes and Conway (2011).

publishing that enabled a paradigm in which a wide variety of economic and political interests were amalgamated and where think tanks, fake journals, paper mills and astroturfing can be found intertwined today under the conditions of the digital transformation of scientific infrastructures.³⁵ This also has an impact on the current age of growing systemic rivalries, which, in Wagner's view, needs to be reflected on more closely: as more and more societies function as knowledge societies, but differences in political systems are once again being emphasised more, science is becoming a weapon in geopolitical disputes with consequences for exchange, standards and norms.

As a result, Wagner believes that some areas of science can no longer be organised competitively in the future. This applies to infrastructures, for which NFDI is cited as an example, but even more comprehensively to digital and technological sovereignty, which are terms that address the sometimes lacking ability to self-regulate in the digital space and the resulting demands on the ability of all scientific actors to act and thus on the resilience of the scientific system as such. From here, the bridge leads to the question of the common good, because it is precisely this that needs to be renegotiated in view of the vulnerability and need for transformation that society has experienced. Sovereignty in the science system should be considered together with the internal and external orientation towards the common good, and procedures should be developed to strengthen the reference to the common good of society while maintaining the sovereignty of the system. As a consequence, research assessment would be reorganised, as the procedures for governance oriented towards the common good and sovereignty would also change the assessment and evaluation procedures with their competitive character.

Based on this assessment, the German Council of Science and Humanities, like the DFG, has therefore signed the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA),³⁶ and the DFG is also involved in the European Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA).³⁷ Even if some of the actions can be seen as inconsistent,³⁸ this development hits on a central point: only if researchers no longer earn their reputation exclusively through high-ranking publications, but also, for example, through the preparation and sharing of data and software, will they also put effort into this and thereby create the basis for transfer to society. Broadening the basis and qualitative evaluation of research achievements is the way to slow down the out-of-control publication system and contribute to the necessary stability and resilience for real innovation. It

³⁵ Cf. Jacquet (2022) 71, 80f., 165ff. and Buranyi 2017.

³⁶ Cf. <https://sfdora.org/>. Accessed on 14/01/2024.

³⁷ Cf. <https://coara.eu/>. Accessed on 14/01/2024.

³⁸ Cf. Brembs (2023).

therefore goes without saying that the profiteers of the subprime impact crisis have also discovered the topic of research assessment reform for themselves.³⁹

Deflate

When asked how the subprime attention crisis could be tackled, Hwang responds with various scenarios,⁴⁰ which come together in the idea of launching a »manageable crisis«. Just as a house in danger of collapse is not simply allowed to break down, but rather blown up in a targeted manner, the air must be released from this bubble in an organised manner before it bursts uncontrollably and causes incalculable damage. In order to manage the crisis, Hwang believes that a functioning alternative is needed at the same time as demolition. The starting point for this is to hit the two pillars that give programmatic advertising its aura of invulnerability: Measurability and effectiveness. If buyers increasingly lose confidence that the current system can achieve their goals effectively and in a clearly measurable way, resources will be freed up for alternatives. This is what makes the reform of research assessment so important for the controlled management of the subprime impact crisis.

Politics is playing a growing role in a comparable manageable crisis in the science sector: just as the rise of programmatic advertising was specifically promoted politically in order to give the still young internet a business model and satisfy economic interests,⁴¹ in the past, science policy and governance had always accepted and desired the competitive structure and the resulting metrics regime, as this - if we go back to its genesis in the 1980s - promised a solution to the dwindling basic funding and the need to tap into other resources. This is beginning to change significantly in the wake of digitalisation and the rise of data-driven research: „The digital transformation“, writes Petra Gehring, „is tearing down the boundary between research activities and infrastructures, between research content and the mere processing or storage of data.“⁴² Infrastructures must and are therefore increasingly being viewed differently in their entirety, which also affects publication infrastructures and the institutions linked to them, such as libraries.

The resolutions of the Council of the European Union (and therefore the member states) on »high-quality, transparent, open, trustworthy and equitable scholarly publishing« should be mentioned prominently here.⁴³ In order to contain the „hazards of scholarly publishing“, the expansion of Diamond Open Access and overarching infrastructures such as the EOSC and Open Research Europe is envisaged. The resolutions were warmly welcomed throughout Europe by the major

³⁹ Cf. e.g. <https://www.elsevier.com/academic-and-government/research-evaluation-and-impact>. Accessed on 14/01/2024.

⁴⁰ Cf. Hwang (2020) 133-137.

⁴¹ Cf. Crain (2021).

⁴² Gehring (2018).

⁴³ See Council of the European Union (2023).

funding organisations, in Germany by the DFG, which in its statement also refers to data tracking as one of the motivations for the change in the publishing system.⁴⁴ At the German federal level, the Council resolutions were incorporated into the National Action Plan for the European Research Area and the commitment to Diamond Open Access and a reform of research assessment was also anchored there,⁴⁵ in a weakened form in the joint federal and state guidelines on Open Access in Germany.⁴⁶

The political will is based on concrete steps that are already being taken in scientific governance: the »Action Plan for Diamond Open Access« is supported by a broad coalition and focuses on supporting and stabilising the fortunately very diverse but small-scale infrastructure of science-led publishing. Increased efficiency through shared resources, improved quality standards and ensuring sustainability are addressed as well as capacity building overall, for which a »non-profit capacity centre for diamond publishing« is to be created.⁴⁷ In Germany, this is to be established through the DFG's call for the creation of a national service centre for improving the performance of Diamond Open Access publishing.⁴⁸

While science policy and governance in both Europe and Germany have consequently begun to move, the same impetus cannot yet be seen in parts of the scientific infrastructure, particularly in the German library sector. So when Ulrich Herb writes: „It also seems somewhat surprising that Germany seems unwavering in its pursuit of transformative Open Access agreements, while elsewhere there is a tendency to move away from these and towards Diamond Open Access“,⁴⁹ he is referring on the one hand to international developments, which are now presenting detailed concepts for Diamond Open Access in response to research such as that by Heather Morrison,⁵⁰ which points to the worrying cost trends and the negative quality developments mentioned.⁵¹ At the same time, however, the libraries are also in question here, because although the open access transformation has always been supported by politicians, realistically there would never have been a DEAL contract if the libraries had not explicitly embraced this and lobbied for it in many cases in order to secure their role, e.g. as a central APC administration centre on campus. The battle for the »information budget« also presents itself as a battle for an advantageous institutional positioning, whereby structures are cemented that will not easily be dissolved again if the international trend later prevails in Germany. In this respect, it is a retro-operation that seeks to

⁴⁴ Cf. DFG (2023).

⁴⁵ Cf. BMBF (2023) 11f.

⁴⁶ Cf. BMBF and KMK (2023) 3f.

⁴⁷ Cf. Ancion, Borrel-Damián, Mounier, Rooryck and Saenen (2022) 5.

⁴⁸ Cf. DFG (2024).

⁴⁹ Herb (2023).

⁵⁰ Cf. Morrison et al. (2021).

⁵¹ See Mounier and Rooryck (2023).

use the inertial forces of some disciplines as leverage in order to restore the role of the library for publishing that it played for reading in analogue times: an inescapable »window to the world« in which both current information and tradition in its breadth could only be accessed through it. In order to achieve this goal, it is evidently prepared to accept disadvantages for areas other than publishing: the limited rules on user tracking and the inadequate implementation of CC licences in the DEAL contracts, for example, mean risks for an uncontrolled outflow of knowledge and technology as well as intellectual property, without research data infrastructures, start-up funding or innovation management, for example, being structurally aware of this or even being able to influence it.

From the point of view of information infrastructures, too, this is not necessarily a good thing, because the concentration on the large publishers and established media types means that the digital incunabula era will never end, even though alternative concepts are available.⁵² It hinders the broadening of recognised research output, which will value publications where they are still important (and thus, together with the relevant disciplines, also helps small and medium-sized publishers and innovative scholarly publishers) and it wilfully restricts libraries to an administrative position - which would still meet Bernhard Fabian's old criticism that libraries would miss the opportunity in digitisation to focus on research-oriented procedures instead of just library-oriented ones.⁵³

„The business case for challenging scientific evidence that implicates a product in a social problem is straightforward“, writes Jennifer Jacquet in »The Playbook« with recognisable derision. „By delaying costly and intrusive science-based regulations, the creation of scientific disagreement buys time and saves money. As with many other cost-saving operations that are perfectly legal, but are nevertheless socially undesirable - such as cutting wages, moving manufacturing to countries with fewer regulations, using offshore tax heavens - the unmaking of scientific agreement must be treated with discretion.“⁵⁴ Libraries know this kind of discretion well enough, be it in licence negotiations with large players or in the spread of data cartels on their own campus, where Lamdan believes that hardly anyone is aware of the linking of individual applications to entire workbenches, as no one has an overview of all workflows.⁵⁵ This makes it all the more important for libraries to be active, which have many players in mind in their everyday lives - but what role did it play, for example, in the negotiations concluded last year with a major publisher that in the past issued marketing material as peer-reviewed journals,⁵⁶ is closely interwoven with the Merchants of Doubt

⁵² Cf. Brembs et al. (2023).

⁵³ Cf. Fabian (1983) 196f.

⁵⁴ Jacquet 2022, p. XVf.

⁵⁵ Cf. Lamdan (2023) 66.

⁵⁶ Cf. Lischka (2009).

of the fossil industry⁵⁷ and aligns its political landscape management accordingly? „And how disappointed would you be?“ wrote Richard Horton as editor of »The Lancet«⁵⁸ - and yet he remained in his position. Is this also the attitude of libraries? When a company emerges among mainstream library supporters whose founder apparently thinks democracy is good above all when the candidates he finances are elected,⁵⁹ how do libraries behave in view of their professional ethics, which emphasise support for democracy?⁶⁰ And if it turns out that publishers and suppliers in the information sector are engaged in widespread data tracking, is it the understanding of integrity and professional competence laid down in the ethic principles that the library associations do not comment on this and negotiators are satisfied with sometimes rather half-baked data protection clauses?

After all, such issues are not about nothing: researchers can withdraw from controversial topics if they fear that they will be persecuted and attacked even more than they already are.⁶¹ Funding organisations may come to the conclusion that funding is not worthwhile if the open door to industrial espionage means that the returns will accrue elsewhere anyway. And even if, as Hwang points out, third-party tracking data in particular is often flawed, the consequences that data analytics systems derive from it can still be devastating, as in the case of the algorithmic decision-making systems that are spreading in the public sector, which have labelled large numbers of benefit recipients as welfare fraudsters. Even though the accusations almost always proved to be false, those affected faced blocked bank accounts, seizures and insolvency proceedings, lost their homes and their social environment, and some took their own lives as a result.⁶²

Part of the subprime attention crisis is the pull with which programmatic advertising draws financial resources away from all media that have grown up with traditional forms of advertising. One symptom of this is the death of newspapers, which is leading to ever larger »news deserts«⁶³ and is also expected to leave 40% of communities in Germany without a local newspaper by 2025.⁶⁴ This deprives a long-time important basis for participation and democratic discourse of its livelihood, while the ad industry all too often diverts funds to platforms that offer disinformation both a stage and funding to maximise user engagement, which is why Hoffman describes them as »partners in

⁵⁷ See Elsevier: Solutions for OIL and GAS. Increase productivity and future-proof with high-quality science and AI, <https://web.archive.org/web/20210923062544/https://www.elsevier.com/rd-solutions/oil-and-gas>, accessed on 14 January 2024, and Westervelt (2022).

⁵⁸ „A question. If you discovered that your organisation had a Political Action Committee that gave money to US Congressional politicians who were anti-science, climate sceptics, and supporters of US disengagement from WHO, what would you do? And how disappointed would you be?“ Richard Horton, tweet from 18.08.2020, <https://twitter.com/richardhorton1/status/1295818198059814921>.

⁵⁹ Cf. Chafkin (2021) in particular 255ff.

⁶⁰ See BID (2017) 2.

⁶¹ See Nogrady (2021).

⁶² See Gilman (2020) and De La Garza (2020).

⁶³ Cf. Abernathy (2024).

⁶⁴ See Kramp and Weichert (2023).

crime«. ⁶⁵ Correspondingly problematic features are shown in the subprime impact crisis, which structurally fuels the replication crisis with the result that the most unreliable research is often published in the most prestigious journals if it is *catchy* enough. ⁶⁶ This only opens the doors further and further for the Merchants of Doubt, their think tanks and paper mills, until the basis for scientific discourse threatens to crumble: there are always the right experts with the right studies for everything and the previously common factual basis becomes the plaything of competing narratives and the half-truths analysed by Nicola Gess. ⁶⁷

A manageable crisis therefore seems just as necessary as the information sector still does not have a functioning alternative and appears to be more a case of »first mover disadvantage« - every player fears disadvantages if they are the first to move. ⁶⁸ Accordingly, there are relatively few libraries in Germany that, for example, play an active role in the NFDI, research experimental foundations for new forms of information provision and develop services from them, or really work vigorously on the implementation of Diamond Open Access through their own resource allocation. In the library sector - in contrast to the computer centres - even fewer approaches for overarching, profile-forming infrastructures in the sense of the Science Council recommendations that actually affect local autonomy can be seen.

What we are seeing in the library sector, on the other hand, are discussions that were initially stimulated more by the classic interventions in free access to information, such as book bans, and from there now extend to the relationship between libraries and politics, the position of libraries in relation to rampant disinformation and the necessary safeguarding of a free society. ⁶⁹ Achim Bonte clearly highlights the contribution that both public and academic libraries can make to alleviating the vulnerability of free societies in the multiple crisis analysed by Dorothea Wagner. This applies to the physical location and its transformation into the »Palaces of the People«, ⁷⁰ but also to the virtual world, where openness as a guiding maxim is not to be understood attributively as in the mental fading stages of open access, where »open access« means nothing more than an open biscuit tin. Rather, openness is a social mandate that also strengthens digital sovereignty:

„If one recognises that the future fate of libraries will depend decisively on digital information infrastructures, it seems only logical, especially for larger institutions, to systematically expand their own evaluation and action competence on the basis of open-source applications and efficient development communities in central product areas such as data management and catalogue development, retro-digitalisation and information visualisation.“ ⁷¹

⁶⁵ Cf. Hoffman (2022) 57-91.

⁶⁶ See Brems (2018).

⁶⁷ See Gess (2021).

⁶⁸ See Boulding and Christen (2001).

⁶⁹ See Degkwitz and Schleihagen (2024).

⁷⁰ See Klinenberg (2018).

⁷¹ Bonte (2024).

Bonte also refers to the Fediverse as an example of this, where the X-alternative Mastodon is also secured by libraries such as the Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin and the TIB Hannover and thus kept resilient and not buyable. It is contributions like these that help to establish functioning alternatives for the subprime impact crisis. „*Freedom for security*. In this area, too, Popper's guiding principle is completely applicable. And libraries are working on it.“⁷²

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⁷² Bonte (2024) 127.

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